

Substitution reactions of ligand bridged multinuclear complexes of platinum group metal ions[†]

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This review discusses the kinetic aspects of the substitutions in various ligand bridge multinuclear complexes of platinum group metal ions. The reactions have been categorized with various bridging bonds and metal ions acting as nuclei. Polymerization of complex compounds involves formation of multinuclear complexes. Kinetics and mechanistic features associated with all such reactions have been highlighted and discussed critically.

Introduction

Studies on the mechanisms of substitution reactions of ligand bridged multinuclear complexes have been done mostly with those of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) ions because of their easy availability and convenience of following their reactions by conventional techniques^{1,2}. Multinuclear complexes of platinum group metals are inert and form complexes which differ in many ways from those of cobalt(III) and chromium(III). These metal ions form new type of bridging compounds displaying new reaction pathways. In this review only the thermal substitution reactions have been described. Redox reactions and photo-substitution reactions have been kept out of the purview of this article. Metal ions of the platinum group are arranged according to their placement in the periodic table (VIII, IX and X, in the long form of periodic table). Complexes containing two different metal nuclei have also been included in this review and placed at the end.

Substitution reactions of metal ion complexes

Ruthenium(II, III, IV) complexes :

Ruthenium in its various oxidation states forms a large number of complexes, which are inert and suitable for mechanistic investigation. However, study on the multinuclear complexes of ruthenium has been taken up at a later date and many of them reveal interesting results.

Aquation of the oxo-bridged complex $[\text{Cl}_5\text{-Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_5]^{4-}$ was investigated in 5 NH_2SO_4 . Ru-O-Ru bond breaks up during chloride substitution by H_2O . Upto five chloride ions are replaced. Activation parameters were derived by assuming initial replacement of two axial chloride followed by replacement of the equatorial chloride³. Aquation of the trinuclear mixed valence complex 'ruthenium

red' $[(\text{H}_3\text{N})_5\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{6+}$ was investigated in aqueous $\text{NH}_4\text{OH-NH}_4\text{Cl}$ buffer. The observed rate constant⁴ at 25° is 10.0 s^{-1} . The analogue of the same compound, 'ruthenium brown' $[(\text{H}_3\text{N})_5\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{-O-Ru}^{\text{IV}}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{7+}$, whose reaction was investigated in presence of OH^- , shows that hydroxide ion is oxidized in a second order process for which the rate constant at 25° is $1.9 \times 10^4\text{ s}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔH^\ddagger is $19.0\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Rapid internal rearrangement and attack of a OH^- ion on the central ruthenium ion, which is least blocked by ligand nitrogen atoms, leads the reaction⁵. The initial stage of the reaction involves rate-determining attack of hydroxide ion on ruthenium and the final product is a Ru-NO species related to ruthenium red; intermediate stages would be expected to involve coordinated hydroxylamine⁶.

The oxo-bridge dimer $\{[(\text{bipy})_2\text{H}_2\text{O.Ru}^{\text{III}}]_2\text{O}\}^{4+}$ is reduced by aqueous acidic solution of L-cystein to cysteine and two mol-equivalent of the monomer $[(\text{bpy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}]^{2+}$. The reaction is first order in each of the redox partners, and the dependence of the second order rate constant (k_2) on 'acid concentration' is given by, $k_2 = a + b[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$. Rate constants and activation parameters with plausible mechanism have been discussed⁷.

The dinitrogen-bridged complex $[(\text{H}_3\text{N})_5\text{Ru-}\mu(\text{N}_2)\text{-Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{6+}$ has an aquation rate constant $\geq 10^3\text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature, much faster than the non-bridged species $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_2]^{3+}$ ⁸. The tetranuclear cation $[\text{Ru}_4(\text{OH})_4]^{8+}$ undergoes depolymerization giving $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{OH})_2]^{4+}$ with a rate constant⁹, $2.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{ s}^{-1}$ at 298 K, $\Delta H = 63\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. In aqueous acidic solution (0.1 M LiCF_3SO_3 , $[\text{H}^+] = 0.01\text{ M}$ at 29.4°) tetrakis- μ -propionatodiruthenium(II,III) cation reacts with oxalate ion in a two-phase process. The first reaction involves replacement of one propionate ligand by

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

oxalate ion. A subsequent slower reaction ($k = 11.3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) occurs whose rate is proportional to the added oxalate ion. This reaction occurs due to the formation of bis(μ -oxalato)bis(μ -propionato)diruthenium(II,III) anion. A third much slower change results in decomposition of the product¹⁰. Mechanistic studies on the bond rupture of the complex $[(\text{CN})_5\text{Ru(II)-L-Ru(II,III)(NH}_3)_5]^{n-}$, where L = CN^- , NC^- , 4,4'-bipy were carried out. The product is ion-pair $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Ru.OH}_2^{2+}.\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$. Rate constant is $(6.7 \pm 1) \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The components are separated by 2-methylpyrazine¹¹. Acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage reaction of two doubly bridged trinuclear complex ions $[\text{Ru}_3(\text{NH}_3)_{13}(\text{SCN})\text{X}_2]^{6+}$, (X = Cl^- , Br^-) have been investigated at 59° in perchloric and nitric acid media, respectively. Both the complexes show two stages of reaction. Plots of k_{obs} vs 'acid concentration' are linear for both the complexes in their both the stages of reactions. The rate constants for the chloro and the bromo complexes for acid-dependent paths are as follows : first stage 5.15×10^{-4} and $2.43 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and second stage 7.35×10^{-3} and $4.02 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. An associative mechanism operates in the process in which bond formation by the incoming solvent (water) molecule with the middle ruthenium atom leads to rupture of bridging bonds¹². Multidentate ligand ethylenebisbiguanide (EBG) $\{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{bigH})_2, \text{bigH} = \text{NH}_2.\text{C}(\text{=NH})\text{NHC}(\text{=NH})\text{NH}_2\}$ with ruthenium(III) forms dinuclear complex where the arms of the ligand acts as bridges. Aquation rate law for the complex $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{EBG})_3]^{6+}$ is $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1[\text{H}^+]$ with the resultant formation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{EBG})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$. At 80°, k_1 is $11.2 \pm 0.3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are $59 \pm 4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-155 \pm 15 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively¹³.

Formation of bridged ruthenium(II, III, IV) complexes :

Formation of the μ -peroxo complex of the type $[\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}\text{L}]_2\text{O}_2$ takes place by the reaction of H_2O_2 with $\text{K}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{PDTA-H})\text{Cl}].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{HPDTA-H})\text{Cl}]$ (PDTA = propylenediaminetetraacetic acid and HEDTA = hydroxyethylenediaminetriacetic acid). Thermodynamic and activation parameters are reported¹⁴. Formation of a cyano-bridged polynuclear *trans*-species was observed by the reaction of $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{OH}_2]^{2+}$ with HCN in 6 M trifluoroacetic acid¹⁵. The immediate product is $[(\text{H}_3\text{N})_5\text{-Ru}(\text{NCH})]^{2+}$, which rearranges in less acidic solutions to the C-bonded isomer with loss of H^+ and then polymerizes.

Formation of binuclear complex $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{NH}_3)_8(\text{SCN})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ was investigated in the temperature range 45–59°. $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ in the presence of excess ammonium thiocyanate forms a SCN^- -bridged complex in a first order process. The reaction follows two paths, one dependent on SCN^- concentration and the other independent of it. It was

shown that the SCN^- -independent path virtually represents aquation of the chloropentaammine complex. The SCN^- with its opposite charge forms ion-association with two complex ions, which finally forms a bridge between the two. Activation parameters are $\Delta H^\ddagger = 96 \pm 8$ and $56 \pm 8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -17 \pm 20$ and $-125 \pm 21 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively, for the first and second stages of reaction¹⁶. Formation of a trinuclear complex ion $[\text{Ru}_3(\text{NH}_3)_{13}(\text{SCN})\text{Cl}_2]^{6+}$ by the reaction of the same two species $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ and SCN^- in the temperature range 30–45° was also investigated. In this temperature range, direct replacement of Cl^- by SCN^- takes place. The thiocyanate ion binds two complex molecular species together and then forms a bridge between the two. No ion-pair formation takes place at any stage of the reaction. As soon as a bridge is formed by the SCN^- ion, the *trans*-chloride of the dinuclear complex forms another bridge with a third complex species in a fast reaction step. Retention of isosbestic points indicates that only one reaction takes place throughout the process without the appearance of any reaction intermediate. Activation parameters have been calculated for various steps, which conforms to an 'associative' mechanism for the reaction¹⁷.

Formation of the thiocyanato-bridged dinuclear complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{-SCN-Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{5+}$ by the substitution of 'aqua' ligand from the species $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{3+}$ by $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{SCN}]^{2+}$ was investigated in the pH range 3.12–6.53 and temp. 32–58°. In this pH range, both aqua and the hydroxo forms of the complex take part in the reaction. The rate constant values (50°) are 12.78×10^{-5} and $23.30 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are 31.8 ± 2 and $37.6 \pm 6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and -225 ± 10 and $-200 \pm 10 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively¹⁸.

Formation of dinuclear complex with ruthenium and other metal ions :

The reaction between two complex species $[\text{Ru}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6]^{3-}$ was investigated in aqueous medium in the pH range 4.00–6.10 and at 21–40°. The plot of k_{obs} vs pH has a bell-shaped profile. It was concluded that only the hydroxo-aqua form $[\text{Ru}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+}$ of the complex is reactive under the experimental conditions and forms the dinuclear complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{BigH})_2-\mu(\text{SCN})_2-\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_4]^{0}$. The values¹⁹ of rate constant for the dinuclear complex formation at 31° is $(2.57 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger $60 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and ΔS^\ddagger $116 \pm 10 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

The formation of binuclear complex in aqueous solution of $[\text{Ru}(\text{edta})\text{L}]^-$ (L = pyz, bipy, dimethylbipyridine or trimethyl bipyridine) and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{3-}$ with kinetic data have been reported²⁰. The binuclear complex is formed through an aqua substitution path and a new metal-to-ligand

charge transfer band for Fe ---- L coordination develops in the visible region. A plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Ru}(\text{edta})\text{L}]^-$ gives a straight-line with a small intercept which signifies a small reversible aquation. The rate of formation (k_f) and aquation reaction (k_r) were obtained from slope and intercept, respectively. The reaction and the rate equation can be given as :

Cyanopyridine-bridged complex $[(\text{CN})_5\text{Fe-L-Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5]$, L = 4- and 3-cyanopyridine were prepared by substitution reaction of $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{L}]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{OH}_2]^{3-}$. Rate constants of formation and dissociation were measured as $k_f \sim 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_d \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The complex hydrolyzes at a faster rate than the corresponding mononuclear ruthenium(III) complex²¹. Rate of bridge cleavage (ring closure) reaction of the ion $[(\text{edta})\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{-NC-Fe}^{\text{III}}(\text{CN})_5]^{4-}$ was measured as $k = 3.0 \pm 0.45 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°, pH 4.8 and ionic concentration 0.66 mol dm^{-3} . Formation of cobalt-edta ion during the redox reaction results not from the bridge-cleavage reaction but rather from the outer-sphere redox process²². The mixed-valence cyanide-bridged complexes $\text{K}_5[(\text{NC})_5\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{-CN-Ru}^{\text{III}}(\text{edta})]$ (M = Fe, Ru or Os) were prepared by mixing hexacyanide species with a solution of $[\text{Ru}(\text{edta})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$. The equilibrium constant for the formation of binuclear complexes were similar for the three complexes and is $(1.5 \pm 0.1) \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The kinetics of formation and dissociation of the binuclear complexes were measured with k_f and k_d showing value nearly independent of M(II), suggesting the onset of associative mechanisms. The rate law for the formation of the mixed-valence complex was as

$$d(\text{M-CN-Ru})/dt = k [\text{M}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] [\text{Ru}(\text{edta})(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-]$$

The rate constant values and the comparative study of the M(II) (M = Fe, Ru or Os) have been reported²³. Kinetics of substitution in $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{3+}$ by the nucleophiles $[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, $[\text{Os}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ in the absence of indifferent electrolyte show that rate constant for substitution (in every case first order in cation concentration) increases as the ratio of the concentration of the nucleophile to the aquo ion increases and then it abruptly becomes independent of this ratio²⁴. At 20°, rate constant values are $(k \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$ 1.5, 2.8 and 1.1 respectively for Ru^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{III} complexes²⁵.

Osmium(III) complexes :

Compared to ruthenium, studies on binuclear complexes

of osmium are rare. The dinuclear osmium(III) complex $[(\text{H}_3\text{N})_5\text{Os}-\mu(\text{N}_2)-\text{Os}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{6+}$ aquates readily, whereas the $\text{Os}^{\text{III}} \text{Os}^{\text{II}}$ mixed-valence cation is independently stable in water. The similarly constituted ruthenium complex is relatively labile⁸. Acid hydrolysis of the CN^- -bridged $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Os}^{\text{III}}-\mu(\text{NCCN})\text{Os}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_5]$ gives $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Os}^{\text{III}}(\text{NH-COCN})\text{Os}^{\text{II}}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{4+}$. At 25°, rate constant²⁶ is $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Rhodium(III) complexes :

Only one study on the cleavage and formation of hydroxide bridged binuclear complex of rhodium(III) is available in the literature. The results of acid catalysis are interpreted in terms of uncatalyzed and acid-catalyzed paths. The rate constants and activation parameters are as follows²⁷ :

At 25°, ΔH^\ddagger (in kJ mol^{-1}), ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), $k_5 = 2.30 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger 107, ΔS^\ddagger 12; $k_2/k_3 = 3.48 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $\Delta H_3^\ddagger = 78$, $k_4 = 3.82 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_4^\ddagger = 116$, $\Delta S_4^\ddagger = 40$, $\Delta S_3^\ddagger = -68$.

The ethylenbisbiguanide complex forming the dinuclear complex undergoes ligand cleavage in acid solution with a rate law : Rate = $Kk [\text{complex}]/(K + [\text{H}^+])$, where K is the protonation constant of the complex species. At 80°, the value¹³ of k is $(2.53 \pm 0.14) \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Acid-catalyzed decarboxylation of $[\text{L-Rh}^{\text{III}}-\mu\{(\text{OH})_2\text{-}(\text{OCO}_2)\}\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}\text{L}]$ (L = 1,4,7-triazacyclononane[9]one N_3) has been reported. The reaction proceeds with the rate law : $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1[\text{H}^+]$. At 303.2 K and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the value²⁸ of $k_1 = (0.60 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Palladium(II) and platinum(II, IV) complexes :

Reaction mechanism and kinetics in the formation and cleavage reaction of $[\text{Pd}_2\text{I}_6]^{2-} + 2\text{I}^- \rightleftharpoons 2[\text{PdI}_4]^{2-}$ were investigated in aqueous medium. The rate laws for the cleavage and reverse reactions are as given in eqns. (1) and (2),

$$-d[\text{Pd}_2\text{I}_6^{2-}]/dt = (k_a + k_b[\text{I}^-] + k_c[\text{I}^-]^2)[\text{Pd}_2\text{I}_6^{2-}] \quad (1)$$

$$-d[\text{PdI}_4^{2-}]/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{PdI}_4^{2-}]^2 \quad (2)$$

The rate constant k_{obs} in eqn. (2) is a function of the concentration. The term $[\text{I}^-]^2$ in eqn. (1) is thought not to be a medium effect, but may correspond to concerted breaking of both Pd-I-Pd bridges. Both $[\text{PdI}_4]^{2-}$ and $[\text{PdI}_3(\text{OH}_2)]^-$ are involved in the mechanism of forward and reverse reactions of the equilibrium of equation as given in the beginning²⁹. Harris and Grey³⁰ studied equilibria in the reaction,

where L = acetonitrile or cyclo-octane and M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}. The equilibria are established more rapidly with palladium complexes and these also have much smaller values of K. For L = MeCN at 21°, $k = 5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for palladium and $10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for platinum³⁰. A more complicated series of reactions involving dinuclear complexes has been studied kinetically by employing NMR line-broadening techniques³¹. The formation of bi-heterometallic complexes, [PdPtCl₄(PBu₃)₂] on mixing chloroform solutions of [M₂Cl₂(PBu₃)₂], where M = Pd or Pt, occurs via attack of dimer on dimer to form a tetrameric intermediate with each metal ion of two dimers bonded to one of the bridging chlorides³².

Halide bridged complex [Pd₂X₄(PPr₃)₂] (X = Cl⁻ or I⁻) is cleaved by 1,4-benzodiazepines to give monomeric complexes in which the benzodiazepine is presumably coordinated through N(4) of the heterocyclic ring. The difference in stability in the various complexes is attributed mainly to the difference in the rate constants corresponding to the reverse reaction³³. Kinetics and mechanistic aspects of sulfur abstraction from sulfur-bridged palladium complexes have been reported³⁴. The complex [Pd₂X₂(μ-S)(μ-dpm)], using dpm or dpm Me [X = halide, dpm = bis-diphenylphosphinomethane and dpm Me = 1,1'-bis-diphenylphosphinoethane] and catalytic conversion of H₂S to H₂. The rate of sulfur abstraction is dependent on halide concentration.

A number of studies on the cleavage of singly, doubly and triply bridged (chloride and sulfide bridges) platinum(II) and palladium(II) complexes have been made recently. The reactions with L may be shown as³⁵⁻⁴²

Di-palladium(II) complex and their platinum(II) analogues react rapidly with five-coordinate rhodium(I) compounds [RhCl₂H(PR₃)₂] to give di-μ-chloro species containing one Rh and Pd or Pt atoms⁴³,

Rates of formation of the products depend strongly on the nature of the phosphines PR₃¹ and PR₃². The rate law for the anation reaction of the dinuclear platinum(III) pyrophosphato- and sulfato-bridged complexes :

and

was investigated and is $k_{\text{obs}} = [\text{complex}] [Y^-]$.

At pH 3.8–4.0 (25°), the values of second order k_{xy} are 0.078, 0.27, 0.37 and 2.8 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ for XY = ClCl, BrCl, BrBr and BrSCN showing little dependence on the incoming nucleophile⁴⁴.

Acid dissociation and dimerization reactions of [Pt(amino acid)(Me₂SO)(H₂O)], where amino acids are glycine, sarcosine, N,N'-dimethylglycine, were investigated. Data for dimerization (k_d and k_{-d})⁴⁵ at 35° are $pK_a = 4$, $k = 100 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $k_d = 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{-d} = 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Formation of platinum(II) complexes with a single pyrazine or dimethyl sulfide bridge by cleavage of the chloride bridge of [(PtCl₂)py(substituent)₂] was investigated in solution. At low temperature a monochloro-bridge structure forms, but the splitting of this bridge leads to the formation of pyrazine or dimethylsulfide-bridged compounds⁴⁶.

Conclusion

In this review kinetic studies have been discussed to explore the mechanistic aspects of substitution reactions in multinuclear complexes of platinum group metal ions. Speciality of platinum group metals is that they form a large number of stable complexes in various oxidation states and significant mechanistic conclusions can be deduced from the reactions of these compounds. Polymerization of complexes involves multinuclear centres, and mechanistic studies of such processes should be taken up more intensely. With recent synthesis of linear trimetallic compounds with metal-metal direct bonds⁴⁷ new field of study of multinuclear complexes emerges out.

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